

EU-CIEMBLy

Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Deliverable 4.2

Report on Online Training of Facilitators

v1

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Authors	Anastasia Karatzia, Niall O'Connor
Contributors	Hendrik Nahr, Guillemette Colombe (Make.org) Maria Tazi Carmela Barbera, Antonella Di Maso, Laura Mariani, Mariafrancesca Sicilia (UniBG) Kathryn McCabe (The Change Agency)
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides an account of the training for facilitators delivered under Task 4.2 of the EU-CIEMBLY project. The training was designed to prepare facilitators for the implementation of local, national, and transnational pilot citizens' assemblies by equipping them with shared conceptual foundations, practical guidance, and reflexive tools for intersectionality-informed facilitation. This training will subsequently be complemented by more targeted briefings in advance of each pilot as to the relevant pilot's organisational logistics and structure.

Deliverable 4.2 documents a collection of training materials developed by the EU-CIEMBLY consortium and provided to facilitators prior to the pilots. It also documents the discussions and reflections generated during the online training session that took place on 19 January 2026, organised by the University of Essex team with contributions from the Make.org and the University of Bergamo teams as well as an external expert, Kathryn McCabe from The Change Agency. Particular attention is given to facilitation as a cross-cutting intervention through which the project seeks to explore the operationalisation of intersectionality in deliberative practices using the three activators of intersectionality-oriented facilitation developed in Deliverable 3.4, namely: valuing diverse modes of communication; understanding how power works in deliberative settings; and practising reflexivity.

The material and training provided were intended to prepare facilitators and to enable discussion on operationalising these three intersectionality activators. The first part of the training was intended to ground the importance of facilitation within the wider context of the EU-CIEMBLY project and our existing deliverables, notably Deliverable 2.2, which provides the project's analytical and normative framework, as well as Deliverable 3.4, which sets out the pilots' marco-design choices. The second part of the training turned to the project's Facilitation Handbook, which addresses all three activators of intersectionality, but with a particular focus in the training session on valuing diverse modes of communication. The third part of the training focused on icebreaking activities, which will be deployed in the pilots to help participants to understand their own diverse backgrounds and experiences while getting to know themselves and each other better, and which relates to the need to be 'reflexive' in an intersectionality-oriented deliberative setting. The fourth part then turned to a consideration of how power works in deliberative settings, notably in small group discussions - i.e., the second of our intersectionality-informed facilitation activators.

All four sessions were grounded in the EU-CIEMBLY project's understanding of intersectionality in deliberative processes, developed in earlier parts of the project, and specifically on the concept of power relations. Accordingly, the concept of *power* was foregrounded in the preparation and the delivery of these sessions and the materials supporting them. Moreover, all facilitators have been invited to take part in a positionality review in advance of the pilots, the results of which are discussed in Deliverable 4.1. This activity followed from a power, privilege, and positionality training session delivered by Karen Bowlby, the University of Essex Inclusion Manager on 13 January 2026 to all Consortium members (reported in Deliverable 4.1). The positionality review exercise for facilitators was developed by the University of Essex team specifically for the EU-CIEMBLY project.

The present report (Deliverable 4.2) consolidates the objectives, content, and outcomes of the facilitator training, thus providing a record of preparatory work for the pilots that will take place under Work Package 4, and establishing a clear link between facilitation design choices and subsequent pilot implementation.

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I. Introduction

1. The Purpose of the Deliverable

EU-CIEMBLY reconsiders the nature and functioning of citizens' assemblies to improve their receptiveness to intersectionality considerations. To achieve this objective, the project deploys what we have named 'targeted interventions'.¹ As already explained in Deliverables 3.4 and 4.1, we have chosen to explore facilitation across all three pilots as an area of intervention that is particularly amenable to accommodating intersectionality considerations within the scope and the inevitable limitations of this project. Deliverable 3.4 (pp. 46-59) set out our **vision for an intersectionality-informed approach to facilitation**, expressed through what we call '**activators of intersectionality**'. These activators apply to all three pilots and form the basis on which we have designed the facilitation activities per pilot. The activators also inform the implementation and evaluation of the facilitation activities and will eventually help us draw broader policy recommendations about the way in which intersectionality can be operationalised through facilitation in citizens' assemblies. As a reminder, the three activators are: (1) valuing diverse modes of communication; (2) understanding how power works in deliberative settings; and (3) practising reflexivity.

The discussion in Deliverable 3.4 explained the reasons *why* experimenting with embedding intersectionality-informed facilitation can further the EU-CIEMBLY project's ambition to contribute to the design of citizens' assemblies as spaces capable of addressing patterns of exclusion and marginalisation that persist within participatory and deliberative innovations. While that deliverable provided the overall vision of facilitation activators that apply to all three pilots, Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 provide further details about specific **activities and guidance** developed for the pilots (Figure 1). In other words, Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 seek to explain *how* we are translating the intersectionality activators into concrete action in the pilots. Deliverable 4.2 in particular focuses on the training programme developed for facilitators, which forms a bridge between the design phase and the implementation of the three pilot assemblies under Work Package 4.

¹ For a detailed discussion, see Deliverable 3.4 Sections I-III.

The present report provides a consolidated account of the training content and outcomes of the online training that took place online 19 January 2026 and brought together facilitators from across the consortium partners as well as an external expert. The training was designed as a shared learning space, combining presentations, discussions, and brainstorming.

Figure 1: The cross-cutting intervention of facilitation across deliverables

2. Structure of the Deliverable

Section II outlines the agenda for the Training Workshop for Facilitators held online on 19 January 2026 and demonstrates the connection of the topics to the three intersectionality-oriented facilitation activators mentioned above. Section III provides an account of the presentations and subsequent discussions. Section IV outlines the next steps for implementation. The content of the training materials provided can be found in the Appendices and are openly available to the facilitators in the project's Google Drive folder.

II. Agenda of the Online Training of Facilitators

The training was structured around four main components: an introduction to facilitation within the EU-CIEMBLY project; the presentation of the EU-CIEMBLY Facilitation Handbook and core guidance; the presentation of a tailored icebreaker developed for the pilots, primarily intended for large groups; and, a dedicated session on positionality, power, and intersectionality in small group facilitation.

The agenda of the training was as follows:

EU-CIEMBLY Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Facilitators Training
19 January 2026

Zoom link: <https://essex-university.zoom.us/j/94542499523?from=addon>

AGENDA

- **08:00-08:15:** Facilitation in the EU-CIEMBLY Project (University of Essex team)
- **08:15-09:45:** Presentation of the EU-CIEMBLY Facilitation Handbook (Make.org team)
- **09:45-10:00:** *Break*

- **10:00-10:30:** Presentation on icebreakers developed for the pilots (University of Bergamo team)
- **10:30-11:00:** *Break*
- **11:00-13:00:** Positionality and Power in Facilitation (Kathryn McCabe, The Change Agency)

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The first session foregrounded the importance of facilitation within the wider context of the EU-CIEMBL Y project and our existing deliverables, notably Deliverable 2.2, which provides the project's analytical and normative framework, as well as Deliverable 3.4, which sets out the pilots' macro-design choices, including the use of facilitation as a cross-cutting targeted intervention. This aligns with the project's **key considerations** for an intersectionality-oriented citizens assembly (Deliverable 3.4). As a reminder, the four key considerations that are used to incorporate intersectionality into our pilots are: (1) the need to be explicit about our normative understanding of intersectionality; (2) being mindful of our own positionality; (3) adopting a context-based approach; (4) choosing deliberate interventions that can take current practices forward. These key considerations are also reflected in the choice of intersectionality in facilitation activators set out above, notably as they relate to the concepts of power and reflexivity.

The second session turned to the EU-CIEMBL Y Facilitation Handbook, which was designed by the Make.org team in collaboration with the University of Bergamo and the University of Essex teams, to address all three activators of intersectionality, with a particular focus in the training session on valuing diverse modes of communication.

The third session of the training focused on some of the icebreaking activities to be deployed in the pilots to help participants to understand their own diverse backgrounds and experiences while getting to know themselves and each other better. This activity highlights the need to be 'reflexive' in an intersectionality-oriented deliberative setting in a way that is accessible and meaningful to participants.

The fourth session then turned to a consideration of how power works in deliberative settings, notably in small group discussion. This training followed from a separate session on power, privilege, and positionality delivered by Karen Bowlby, the University of Essex Inclusion Manager on 13 January 2026 to the Consortium as a whole and which assisted facilitators in preparing their positionality review to be conducted in advance of the pilots (see Deliverable 4.1 for further details).

III. The Facilitators Training Workshop

The training aimed at ensuring that all facilitators share a common understanding of the EU-CIEMBLY's framework and objectives, and that they are equipped to facilitate deliberation in an intersectionality-informed way. As such, it included presentations and discussions on how to recognise and respond to power dynamics in group discussions, and on engaging in reflective and reflexive practices before, during, and after the pilots. As mentioned above, the training was designed as a shared learning space, combining material, discussions, and brainstorming.

The training session was opened by Anastasia Karatzia, who chaired and acted as a moderator throughout the meeting.

1. Setting the Scene: Facilitation in EU-CIEMBLy

The opening segment of the training, delivered by Niall O'Connor, situated facilitation within the broader EU-CIEMBLy methodology. Facilitation was presented as a cross-cutting intervention, central to embedding intersectionality across all three pilots rather than as being a purely technical or neutral aspect of the pilots. The presentation explained the relationship between facilitation and intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. It also recalled the three intersectionality activators previously developed by the project team, which are set out in Deliverable 3.4 and reiterated above.

The presentation can be found in Appendix 2.

2. Presentation of the EU-CIEMBLY Facilitation Handbook

In the next section of the training session, Hendrik Nahr and Guillemette Colombe presented the **EU-CIEMBLY Intersectionality-Informed Handbook to Facilitate a Citizens' Assembly**, which was developed for the project by the Make.org team in collaboration with the University of Bergamo and the University of Essex teams. After setting out the connection to the facilitation intersectionality activators used by the project, the Handbook is divided into 10 substantive parts, each dealing with a broad issue. These include: (1) an overall introduction to what it means to be a facilitator and the goals of facilitation; (2) the attitude that should be displayed by facilitators; (3) the role of a facilitator within the context of the EU-CIEMBLY project; (4) the key skills and attributes of an effective facilitator; (5) the development of house rules for the pilot assemblies; (6) reacting to unexpected situations and developing a 'Plan B'; (7) the importance of icebreakers in helping participants to adjust to an uncertain or unfamiliar environment; (8) the importance of logistics and planning in facilitation; (9) a final reminder that facilitation is an ongoing learning process; and (10) further resources for deepening insights into facilitation from both a theoretical and a practical perspective.

The session provided concrete guidance on managing common facilitation challenges, including how to handle strong disagreement and conflict; how to support quieter or less confident participants; how to manage off-topic discussions; and how to respond to emotional moments.

The presentation led to a fruitful discussion and exchange of ideas among the team. The group discussed strategies for facilitators to avoid creating hierarchical dynamics with participants, emphasising the importance of **clear communication about the facilitators' role**. They explored techniques for **managing challenging scenarios** such as strong disagreement, emotional responses, and dominant participants. Suggested actions included acknowledging concerns, using time management, and encouraging participation through structured activities. The discussion also covered how to handle silent groups, with recommendations to use writing exercises and pair conversations to encourage engagement. Interestingly, some team members expressed commonalities between their experiences as higher education lecturers and their forthcoming role as facilitators, in that educators are also expected to manage small group dynamics although as experts on the topic (something not expected from facilitators).

Issues around **language** were also raised during the exchanges between the participants. Alice Leal noted that the level of confidence of the participants with the spoken language of the assembly directly affects their experiences. The group agreed that the same might happen with facilitators: some of the facilitators in our group (and potentially in other citizens' assemblies) will not be native speakers of English (the primary language of our pilot citizens' assemblies), and this might affect their facilitation style and confidence. The group agreed that being very open about this challenge and asking for support from the rest of the team can mitigate this challenge.

Intersectionality-oriented facilitation

The principles presented in this handbook are guided by the three **intersectionality activators in facilitation**.

These three principles ensure that intersectionality is taken into account when facilitating a workshop or panel, in order to encourage fruitful debates among diverse participants.

The discussion then turned to the importance of giving space and allowing people to share personal stories during the assembly. As mentioned during the presentation, **personal stories** are precious insights on a topic and offer valuable learnings, takeaways, and points for discussion in deliberative settings. It can be fruitful to have such personal stories of lived experiences, so we want to encourage participants to share them. To be encouraged means to have the safety that what is said can stay in the room if that is what the participant wishes. In that vein, Hendrik Nahr emphasised that facilitators need to be mindful and proactive in checking with participants if they prefer that their stories remain confidential or are documented in the outcomes of the discussions.

YOUR ROLE

When you facilitate, it is important to **internalise and reflect** on the fact that **your position differs** significantly from that of the participants. Recognising this distinction is essential for effective facilitation.

Note that for all EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies, facilitators will **undergo a positionality review**.

"Remember that you are not an expert in the topic of the deliberation. If participants have a question on the topic itself, you are not expected to provide a response. Consult the assembly's expert committee when needed."

Another point of the presentation that yielded a vivid discussion was the **skills** that facilitators must apply when facilitating, such as being a good listener, a clear communicator, and a good observer of the dynamics in the room. Among other issues, the group discussed strategies to break down **power dynamics** that exist between facilitators and participants. Here, the emphasis was on how facilitators introduce themselves and their roles to the participants as people who are there to steer and guide the group during their assembly experience. It was also mentioned that having the facilitators participate in the icebreaking activity might help with addressing these power dynamics.

SKILLS TO APPLY WHEN FACILITATING 🙌

1 Be a good listener
 Pay attention to what is said and how it is said.
Example: nod, keep eye contact, repeat a few key words to show you understand what is being said.

2 A clear summariser
 Repeat the main ideas clearly and fairly.
Example: "So far I hear three ideas: better communication, more transparency and simpler rules. Is that right?"

3 A timekeeper
 Make sure the group moves forward without rushing.
Example: "We have ten minutes left, let's hear one more view before we close this topic."

4 A calm and serene mediator
 Let people disagree but stay respectful.
Example: "You see this differently, and that's valuable. Let's explore why."

5 A neutral guide
 Don't give your opinion.
Example: if someone asks, "What do you think?" say, "My role is to help you think together, not to share my view."

6 An encouraging host
 Invite others in.
Example: "I'd like to hear from someone who hasn't spoken yet."

7 A clear communicator
 Use short and very simple sentences with simple language accessible to all.
Example: Avoid complicated words

8 A good observer of the dynamics in the room
 Notice energy and mood.
Example: "It feels a bit quiet, maybe we take a short stretch break."

9 An empathetic presence
 Acknowledge people's emotions in the room.
Example: "I can see this topic matters to you, thank you for sharing. Would you like to tell us more about it? Or would you like us to change the subject?"

10 A connector of ideas
 Help the group see the general picture of what they share, always come back to common ground to advance the conversation towards the agreed output you have to achieve by the end of the day.
Example: "It sounds like everyone agrees that X is essential, even if you differ on X."

The **Intersectionality-Informed Handbook to Facilitate a Citizens' Assembly** that was presented by the Make.org team can be found in Appendix 3.

3. Ideas for an Intersectionality-Oriented Icebreaker

In the Facilitation Handbook, the importance of **icebreakers** was recognised as a means of creating a welcoming and supportive environment. Accordingly, in the next session of the training, Carmela Barbera took the floor to present a suggestion for a larger scale intersectionality-oriented icebreaker developed by the University of Bergamo team for the pilots. The activity was designed to build trust and relationality and to introduce intersectional reflection in accessible ways that are combined with creating a friendly atmosphere during the first session of an assembly. In this way, the project seeks to integrate positionality and reflexivity from the very outset of the pilot assemblies through the icebreaker activities. This will allow all facilitators and participants to understand and appreciate how privilege and power (or underprivilege and disempowerment) can affect deliberation and decision-making in the context of citizens' assemblies.

The proposed main icebreaking activity to be conducted within the pilots draws on the 'Wheel of Privilege', which has been explained in Deliverable 3.4 as a mechanism for understanding sites of privilege and marginalisation. We propose to use a 'theatre-based' icebreaking activity to encourage movement between and among participants, providing adjustments for those less able to move. These activities will also be adapted to the online pilots, as explained in Carmela's presentation. This exercise will not only help break the ice but also assist us as a team to learn what aspects, relationships and dynamics we will need to pay attention to during the deliberation. The idea is that we will open with less challenging questions to warm the participants up, before

moving on to reflect more deeply on their positionality in relation to the topic of our pilot assemblies, namely housing.

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. On the left, a slide titled "For icebreaking purposes..." lists three activities: "Micro-pair reflection", "One word round", and "One-word wall (online-friendly)". The slide also features the EU-CIEMBLY logo and the tagline "Democracy for All". On the right, a grid of video feeds shows approximately 15 participants, each with their name and a small profile picture.

For icebreaking purposes...

Micro-pair reflection
Participants briefly turn to the person/s next to them and share a couple of insights and/or feelings that emerged during the exercise.

One word round
Participants who feel comfortable may share one word describing how the activity made them feel (e.g. curious, aware, surprised); others may simply listen or express similar or different feelings.

One-word wall (online-friendly)
Participants write one word or short phrase on a post-it or shared digital board about what they bring into the Assembly and/or about their feelings/perceptions/thoughts/expectations.

Adhering to the interactive spirit of the workshop, the floor was opened to the participants for Q&A and discussion. The group discussed ways to manage participants who may be reticent or hesitant to share their own positionality through anonymous exercises, such as placing a post-it on a board. We collectively reflected on techniques that we can use to reassure participants of the nature of this exercise and of the safety of the space. One way to do this is to frame questions around the societal and structural barriers that place people in a disadvantaged and underprivileged positions (e.g., ‘Do you feel that current government programmes support you in buying your own house?’) instead of focusing on individual identities (‘Can you buy your own house?’). This approach remains true to the normative understanding of intersectionality in the project, whereby intersectional exclusion and marginalisation are understood as the products of overlapping power relations.

The presentation can be found in Appendix 4.

4. Positionality and Power in Facilitation

In the final part of the presentation, Kathryn McCabe, an external speaker from The Change Agency, delivered a session dedicated to positionality and power in small-group facilitation. Facilitators were invited to reflect on their own experiences and positions of privilege and marginalisation and on how these may shape facilitation dynamics. Drawing on her experience with facilitating a residential programme for 100 diverse teenagers, Kathryn emphasised the importance of moving beyond diversity to achieve true inclusion. The group engaged in an activity whereby participants shared their feelings about the project, with some expressing enthusiasm and others anticipation about the pilot assemblies.

Intersectional Facilitators are people who

- care,
- educate themselves; understand their context of power and oppression,
- know their privilege, and uses it well,
- curate a space for those typically marginalised to take up more space,
- follow the leaderships of marginalised communities,
- are active bystanders,
- act in situations of discomfort,
- speak in situations of tension; that name the moment, accepts it and curiously enquires about it,
- step in, name the issue/system, rather than focusing only on the personal,
- accept feedback, seek feedback,
- use their own privilege to create change.

The presentation made participants aware of broader systems of oppression and how they may surface in deliberation. Kathryn introduced positionality as a reflexive practice, allowing us to identify patterns of covert oppression and marginalisation and to remain alert to the risks of collapsing inclusion or indeed intersectionality into broader conceptions of ‘diversity’. In relation to facilitation, it was noted that no one’s actions can be truly ‘neutral’ but are rather shaped by and in turn shape wider societal structures. In this sense, the objective of embedding positionality in facilitation is to see biases as well as the structures that uphold them, and to render them *more* visible through our intersectionality activators. Achieving this objective requires both ‘learning’ and ‘unlearning’ to mitigate these same biases and structures.

Approaches to foster as facilitators

Strengthen perspective of **mutual interest**

Value others perspectives, views and experiences as **equally valid**

Apply ethics; nuanced, curious, firm when necessary

Develop comfort with tension and uncertainty

Accept we are imperfect, practice being open to making **mistakes** and hearing feedback

Manage response to own 'triggers'

Relational; Values **process** and not just outcome

Seeks connection, builds relationships and fosters **conditions for consent**

One of the most notable aspects of this part of the training was Kathryn's points on privilege and positionality. She stated that power makes people uncomfortable in terms of their own positionality in power. People who have experienced marginalisation are very aware of the ways in which those in privilege hold power and may be frustrated by the lack of acknowledgment of power imbalances in certain contexts. As such, it is imperative for us as a project to be clear from the beginning about challenges (either in participation or in housing problems), about why people experience those challenges, and about the fact that people are experiencing these challenges is deeply rooted in social systems and oppressive structures as opposed to deriving purely from their own individual identities or actions.

The presentation can be found in Appendix 5.

IV. Conclusion and Next Steps

The training session and the accompanying material in this Deliverable mark an important step in translating our activators of intersectionality-informed facilitation into practice, thereby furthering our aims of operationalising intersectionality in the design and delivery of citizens' assemblies as democratic innovations. The three activators: valuing diverse modes of communication; understanding power in deliberative settings; and practising reflexivity, are inherently interconnected and cannot be understood in isolation. As such, these activators will pervade all aspects of the design of the facilitation for the three pilot citizens' assemblies to be tested at the local, national, and transnational levels.

While training is essential to ensuring good facilitation, it is also necessary to reflect on the fact that a proper understanding of positionality requires constant reflexive practice. It is important to remain aware of one's own positionality and its impact on our relations with other people, including the pilots' participants who will bring their own positionality to the intersectionally equal and inclusive deliberative space we are seeking to create. All of the facilitation team were invited to engage in a positionality exercise that was designed to encourage both reflection and reflexion on the influence of privilege and marginalisation on the *role* of facilitator and on the *process* of facilitation. Further dedicated briefing sessions for facilitators will be held in advance of the local, national, and transnational pilots, starting with the local pilot in Colchester.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Participant List

Carmela Barbera, University of Bergamo

Laura Mariani, University of Bergamo

Maria Francesca Sicilia, University of Bergamo

Niall O'Connor, University of Essex

Anastasia Karatzia, University of Essex

Rebecca Warren, University of Northumbria

Hendrik Nahr, Make.org

Guillemette Colombe, Make.org

Lou Aubay, Make.org

Larissa Humbert, Make.org

Manon Basset, Make.org

Rita Douteiro Brites, Make.org

Sarah Noles, IMI

Alice Leal, WITS

Antonis Karatzias, ASPON

Alexandros Patraourides, ASPON

Maria Georgiou, ASPON

Anastasios Zografos, ASPON

Avgoustinos Karatzias, ASPON

Giulia Sandri, ECAS

Kathryn McCabe, The Change Agency

Appendix 2. Facilitators Training Introductory Session

The slide features a colorful geometric background on the left side with shades of red, orange, yellow, green, blue, and purple. It contains several logos and text elements:

- Funded by the European Union**: A white box containing the European Union flag logo and the text "Funded by the European Union".
- EU-CIEMBLY Democracy for All**: The logo with five stylized human figures in different colors (red, orange, yellow, green, blue) holding hands, with the text "EU-CIEMBLY" and "Democracy for All" below it.
- University of Essex**: A red square logo with a white grid pattern and the text "University of Essex".
- Facilitators Training**: The main title in a large, bold, blue font.
- 19 January 2026**: The date of the session in a bold black font.
- Disclaimer**: A small text block at the bottom right stating: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694. This deliverable reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for its content or any use that may be made of the information it contains."

Agenda

- **08:00-08:15:** Facilitation in the EU-CIEMBLY Project (Essex team presenting)
- **08:15-09:45:** Presentation of the EU-CIEMBLY Facilitation Handbook (Make.org team presenting)
- **09:45-10:00:** *Break*
- **10:00-10:30:** Presentation on icebreakers developed for the pilots (Bergamo team presenting)
- **10:30-11:00:** *Break*
- **11:00-13:00:** Presentation on Positionality and Power in Facilitation (Kathryn McCabe presenting)

Facilitation in the EU-CIEMBLY Project

Key Considerations in Incorporating Intersectionality into the Design of the Pilots

Targeted Intersectional Interventions

Cross-Cutting Intervention: Embedding Intersectionality in Facilitation

Activators of Intersectionality-Informed Facilitation

Appendix 3. EU-CIEMBLY Facilitation Handbook

INTRODUCTION

This intersectionality-informed handbook is provided to the EU-CIEMBLY (Horizon) project to support the **facilitation of its pilot assemblies**. EU-CIEMBLY examines intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, first from a **theoretical** perspective and then from a **practical** one.

To explore the practical dimension, three pilot projects will be implemented to **test the theoretical approaches** and hypotheses developed within the project, taking place at the local level in Colchester, the national level in Cyprus, and at a transnational level (online).

To ensure high-quality facilitation and a consistent approach across all pilots, this handbook outlines the **knowledge** required, the key **skills** expected, and a range of practical **tips** that will help facilitators implement the pilots effectively. The handbook is directed primarily to facilitators.

Intersectionality-oriented facilitation

The principles presented in this handbook are guided by the three **intersectionality activators in facilitation**.

These three principles ensure that intersectionality is taken into account when facilitating a workshop or panel, in order to encourage fruitful debates among diverse participants.

The handbook is written based on the **ALL HANDS PRINCIPLE**, meaning that most important elements are organised around ten key points - one for each finger - making the content easier to remember and apply in practice.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Lead-Author:

Maria TAZI, Facilitator & International Project Manager at Make.org

Maria brings hands-on experience from some of Europe's most significant deliberative democracy processes. She has facilitated several European Citizens' Panels at the institutional level, coordinated multilingual and intercultural deliberations, and led participatory formats such as the EQUALS-EU Horizon Europe pan-European hackathons. Her work spans Europe, global and online environments, creating inclusive spaces where participants can engage meaningfully.

Supporting

Hendrik NAHR, Head of European Affairs at Make.org

author:

*"Hello! I'm **Fenn, the Facilitation Fairy**. I'll be your guide through this handbook, drawing on Maria's and Hendrik's experiences. You'll see me pop up here and there to share my hands-on ten-cents: little tips and tricks to help you along the way. I hope my guidance makes facilitating your pilot assembly a little easier... and a lot more fun!"*

- 1 FACILITATION
- 2 ATTITUDE
- 3 YOUR ROLE
- 4 SKILLS
- 5 HOUSE RULES
- 6 PLAN B
- 7 ICEBREAKERS
- 8 LOGISTICS
- 9 FINAL REMINDER
- 10 GOING FURTHER

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A slide with a white background and a colorful geometric footer. The footer consists of several colored rectangles in shades of red, orange, yellow, green, and blue. In the top right corner, there is the EU-CIEMBLY logo with the tagline 'Democracy for All'. The word 'FACILITATION' is written in large, bold, black capital letters on the left. Below the title, there are three paragraphs of text. In the bottom right corner, there is a small illustration of a purple pen writing on a blue surface, with several yellow stars around it.

FACILITATION

A citizens' assembly brings together people from **different backgrounds** to **learn, talk and make collective recommendations** on an important issue. The facilitator's job is to make sure **everyone feels heard** and that the conversation stays fair, respectful and useful.

As a facilitator, **you are in control** of your room. Concretely, that means that you set the tone, hold the space, and carry the responsibility to make sure everyone feels safe and heard. You are also responsible for **guiding the group** towards a clear and useful output by the end of the day, in line with the overall project goals and rollout plan.

You are free to **adjust the method** as you see fit (adjust your breaks, your icebreakers for example), but make sure the outcome is relevant at the end of the day.

“

Good facilitation isn't about providing knowledge. But helping others find their voice.

FACILITATION MAIN GOALS

- 1 Ensure everyone has a voice**
 Actively invite contributions from all participants, paying attention to those who may be quieter or less confident.
- 2 Keep the group focused & calm**
 Manage the pace and flow of discussion, preventing distractions or off-topic tangents from taking over.
- 3 Foster listening & understanding**
 Encourage participants to listen carefully to each other, clarifying and summarizing points when necessary to enhance mutual understanding.
- 4 Encourage common ground without forcing agreement**
 Support the group in identifying shared perspectives while respecting differing opinions.
- 5 Create a positive & inclusive space**
 Cultivate an environment of respect, openness, and trust where diversity of thought is valued.
- 6 Stay neutral and impartial**
 Avoid imposing your own views; your role is to guide the process, not the content.
- 7 Manage group dynamics and power imbalances**
 Be aware of who dominates conversations and who holds back, and intervene to ensure balanced participation.
- 8 Adapt methods as needed**
 Adjust facilitation techniques, breaks, icebreakers or activities in response to the group's energy, engagement, or specific needs.
- 9 Maintain attention on outcomes**
 Keep the group aligned with the agreed goals and rollout plan, ensuring the discussion produces recommendations that are in line with the expected results (as set ahead of the assembly).
- 10 Model constructive & respectful behavior**
 Demonstrate the communication and interaction style you want participants to follow, including patience, curiosity, and openness.

ATTITUDE

2

ATTITUDE

A good facilitator creates both **structure** and a sense of **safety**, enabling the group to take genuine ownership of the conversation.

When everyone clearly understands **their respective roles**, the assembly evolves into a space where authentic listening can take place and collective intelligence can emerge. In such an environment, **participants feel empowered** to contribute openly, and the facilitator can guide the process without dominating it.

"Facilitators should allow the group's insights, experiences, and creativity to shape the outcome."

ATTITUDE

POINTS TO GET IT RIGHT

1 Stay calm and patient

Your composure sets the tone for the group; even if discussions become heated or confusing, a calm facilitator helps participants feel safe and focused.

2 Don't fear silences

Give participants time to reflect and think before they speak; meaningful contributions often come after a pause, not immediately.

3 Use simple, clear language

Avoid jargon or overly complex phrasing; clear communication ensures everyone can follow and participate equally.

4 Show respect for all

Acknowledge and value diversity in age, culture, gender, and experience; this fosters an inclusive environment where everyone feels heard.

5 Value every contribution

Even off-topic comments matter; note them and gently guide the conversation back to the main topic, showing participants their input is recognised.

6 Help the group work together

Encourage collaboration and collective problem-solving rather than individual competition; this builds trust and collective ownership of outcomes.

7 Be mindful of power dynamics

Recognise how intersecting power dynamics (such as authority, confidence, social status) affect participation, and work deliberately to amplify quieter or marginalised voices.

8 Be alert to who takes space

Observe participation patterns; actively invite input from those who speak less to ensure balanced engagement.

9 Make sure people have fun

A friendly, positive atmosphere helps participants relax and engage; smiling, light humor, and encouragement create a welcoming environment.

10 Encourage curiosity

Foster a mindset of exploration by asking open questions and inviting participants to consider perspectives different from their own; this deepens dialogue and broadens understanding.

YOUR ROLE

YOUR ROLE

When you facilitate, it is important to **internalise and reflect** on the fact that **your position differs** significantly from that of the participants. Recognising this distinction is essential for effective facilitation.

Note that for all EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies, facilitators will **undergo a positionality review**.

For this reason, the following section **outlines ten key points** that explain why the facilitator's experience differs substantially from the perspective of participants.

"Remember that you are not an expert in the topic of the deliberation. If participants have a question on the topic itself, you are not expected to provide a response. Consult the assembly's expert committee when needed."

SKILLS

4

SKILLS

Facilitating a citizens' panel or assembly is not something that necessarily comes naturally. You may have experience with moderations, workshops, public speaking, or similar formats - or you may have none at all. In either case, this is not a problem.

This handbook is designed to support you throughout the process and to help you feel confident in your role.

A central element of effective facilitation is an awareness of the key skills involved. In the following section, we outline the ten core competencies that are most relevant for you to apply as a facilitator.

“

**Facilitation is not rocket science - you can do it!
Find out how.**

SKILLS TO APPLY WHEN FACILITATING

1 Be a good listener
Pay attention to what is said and how it is said.
Example: nod, keep eye contact, repeat a few key words to show you understand what is being said.

2 A clear summariser
Repeat the main ideas clearly and fairly.
Example: "So far I hear three ideas: better communication, more transparency and simpler rules. Is that right?"

3 A timekeeper
Make sure the group moves forward without rushing.
Example: "We have ten minutes left, let's hear one more view before we close this topic."

4 A calm and serene mediator
Let people disagree but stay respectful.
Example: "You see this differently, and that's valuable. Let's explore why."

5 A neutral guide
Don't give your opinion.
Example: if someone asks, "What do you think?" say, "My role is to help you think together, not to share my view."

6 An encouraging host
Invite others in.
Example: "I'd like to hear from someone who hasn't spoken yet."

7 A clear communicator
Use short and very simple sentences with simple language accessible to all.
Example: Avoid complicated words

8 A good observer of the dynamics in the room
Notice energy and mood.
Example: "It feels a bit quiet, maybe we take a short stretch break."

9 An empathetic presence
Acknowledge people's' emotions in the room.
Example: "I can see this topic matters to you, thank you for sharing. Would you like to tell us more about it? Or would you like us to change the subject?"

10 A connector of ideas
Help the group see the general picture of what they share, always come back to common ground to advance the conversation towards the agreed output you have to achieve by the end of the day. **Example:** "It sounds like everyone agrees that X is essential, even if you differ on X."

A slide titled 'HOUSE RULES' with the EU-CIEMBLY logo in the top right. It contains a quote in a speech bubble, a paragraph of text, and a handshake icon. The background features a colorful geometric pattern at the bottom.

Facilitators need to be neutral in terms of content - but not the process

HOUSE RULES

Setting clear house rules at the start of a session helps create a safe and respectful environment where everyone feels comfortable contributing. These guidelines provide a shared understanding of how the group will interact, fostering trust and ensuring that the discussion runs smoothly.

Remind everyone of these rules at the outset and confirm that all participants agree before beginning. If possible, write them on a visible board or screen, and don't hesitate to refer back to them during the session whenever necessary.

HOUSE RULES

SUGGESTIONS

One person speaks at a time

Listen with respect, even when you disagree

Speak for yourself using "I think" or "I feel"

Stay on topic as much as possible

Respect facilitators' time frame

Every voice matters equally

Disagreement is normal, but keep it kind and constructive

Personal stories stay in the room if the participant prefers it.

Try to understand before you react

Any verbal, physical, racist, or misogynistic comment will not be tolerated

If this happens, kindly but firmly ask the person to leave the room.

PLAN B

PLAN B

Even with careful planning, citizens' panels and assemblies rarely go exactly as expected. **Unexpected situations** can arise, such as disagreements, strong emotions, disruptions, or technical issues if technology is involved. They may challenge the flow of discussion.

Being prepared for these possibilities is key to maintaining a safe, respectful, and productive environment.

The following ten **scenarios** highlight common challenges facilitators may face and provide practical strategies for addressing them, helping you respond calmly, confidently, and effectively while keeping the group focused on meaningful dialogue

If issues arise, keep calm and composed, and take inspiration from the following scenarios!

Scenario 1

Strong disagreement

Disagreements are natural and can even enrich the discussion, but they can quickly escalate if participants talk over each other or become confrontational. The facilitator's role is to slow the conversation down and create space for each person to be heard.

"Let's slow down and take turns. I'll give each of you a minute to explain your point, then we'll explore connections."

"It sounds like we have different views. Let's take time to understand each other."

"Remember, our goal is understanding, not convincing."

Scenario 2

Discussion loses focus

Groups may drift off-topic or get caught in side discussions. Facilitators must gently guide participants back without dismissing their ideas, showing that all contributions are valued but that time is limited.

"That's an interesting idea. Let's note it on the side and return to our main question."

Scenario 3

A participant becomes emotional

Discussions on meaningful topics can trigger strong feelings. Facilitators need to acknowledge emotions and create a safe space for expression without letting the conversation derail.

"Thank you for sharing. Let's take a short break. Your feelings show how important this topic is, and we want to keep a safe space for everyone."

Scenario 4

Criticism of the process

Participants may question or challenge the structure, methods, or purpose of the assembly. Facilitators should listen and acknowledge concerns without defensiveness, keeping the focus on the discussion and maintaining a positive environment.

"This assembly is part of a research process. It isn't perfect, but every voice helps us learn and improve. I'll note your concern for the organising team."

"We're here to discuss the topic, not the process itself. Let's keep this space respectful and productive."

Scenario 5

Verbal aggression

Strong emotions may sometimes lead to disrespectful behavior. Facilitators must intervene calmly to uphold group norms and ensure all participants feel safe to contribute.

"I hear that this topic brings strong feelings, but we need to maintain a respectful tone so everyone feels safe to speak."

Scenario 6

Harassment, Racist, or Misogynist Comments

Any form of harassment or discriminatory language is unacceptable. Facilitators must address these behaviours immediately and clearly, prioritising the safety of all participants.

"That comment is not acceptable. We do not tolerate racist, sexist, or harassing language. Please step outside while we continue respectfully."

Scenario 7

Running behind time

When participants consistently arrive late after small breaks, it can disrupt the group and affect timing. Facilitators should address punctuality politely and encourage respect for everyone's time.

"Let's all return on time so we can make the most of our discussions and respect everyone's schedule."

Scenario 8

Dominating the conversation

Some participants naturally speak more than others, which can unintentionally silence quieter voices. Facilitators should monitor participation and encourage balanced contributions while respecting everyone's right to speak.

"We have heard a lot from you already. Let's hear from someone who hasn't spoken yet."

"I'd like to check if anyone with a different view wants to add something."

Scenario 9

Total silence or shy group

Some groups may be reserved, hesitant to speak, or intimidated. Facilitators can encourage participation by starting with personal, low-stake questions and gradually connect participants to the topic.

"What part of town are you from?"

"Do you have children /grandchildren?"

"It sounds like X is important to you. How does this relate to our discussion?"

"Let's take a minute to write ideas down, then share one each."

Scenario 10

Online technical issues (if online)

Technical issues are common in virtual sessions and can disrupt focus. Facilitators should keep the discussion moving while helping organisers (or participants) resolve issues efficiently, maintaining energy and

"We'll pause briefly to fix the issue. Thanks for your patience."

"If you get disconnected, rejoin with the same link. We'll catch you up."

ICEBREAKERS

Icebreakers help people relax and connect at the beginning of each session. Choose one depending on time and context and adjust it according to your topic at stake.

Quick round (5 minutes)

- Ask: "Share one word that describes how you feel right now."

Post-its all around (5 minutes)

- Give everyone a card or post-it
- Ask: "What do you hope to learn or share today?"
- Collect them and read a few aloud.

Common interests (10 minutes)

- Split into small groups.
- Ask: "Find three things you all have in common that have nothing to do with this assembly."

Common values or developing empathy between participants (10 minutes)

- Example : Ask everyone to stand up (if they can) and move to a place in the room that matches their experience or feeling about a topic. For example: "Move to the left if you feel confident speaking in public, move to the right if it's something you find difficult."

Once everyone has moved, let them quietly notice where others stand. No words are needed! The power of this exercise comes from seeing that others have lived very different realities. If you want to, you can also ask a one or two people: "What makes you feel that way?" or "Have you an anecdote you would like to share with us?"

It's a good way to develop empathy amongst a group of people who don't know each other, with or without needing to speak.

“

Icebreakers can be big surprises. Participants will get to know each other better. And so will you.

LOGISTICS

8

LOGISTICS OFFLINE

Every facilitator should be prepared for **unexpected situations**. Before the session, agree on a clear crisis plan with all facilitators and organisers. Identify a designated organiser or person of authority who can be signaled **if a participant needs to leave** due to racist, violent, or inappropriate behaviour.

Familiarise yourself with the venue's exits, and keep key **contact numbers visible**, including on-site security or the lead event coordinator, as well as emergency or medical services in case someone feels unwell.

If a serious issue arises, remain calm, **prioritise the safety of the group**, and allow the designated organiser to take over the situation. Being prepared in advance ensures a safe, smooth, and well-managed session for everyone.

Remember to have a crisis plan aligned with all facilitators and organisers.

LOGISTICS ONLINE

1

Acknowledge reduced social contact

Actively create moments for connection and check-in on participants' engagement and well-being.

2

Create intentional "coffee-breaks"

Schedule short breaks, using breakout rooms for casual chats or opening the floor for informal conversation.

3

Use online-friendly icebreakers

Start sessions with simple, low-pressure icebreakers (polls, chat questions) to warm up the group and reduce distance between participants.

4

Use clear and inclusive language

Since this is a transnational pilot, speak slowly, avoid jargon and idioms, explain key terms, and encourage participants to ask questions.

5

Use online voting and feedback tools

Use polls or reaction buttons to quickly gather opinions, prioritise ideas, and keep participants highly involved.

6

Test the technical set-up in advance

Ensure familiarity with the platform, test audio/video, and have a back-up plan.

7

Be flexible with camera use

Encourage cameras on to foster connection, but respect participants' constraints, and offer alternative ways to engage (chat, reactions,...).

8

Maintain attention and energy levels

Use shorter sessions, regular breaks, varied activities, and visual tools to keep attention focused and energy balanced.

9

Ensure inclusive participation rules

Clearly explain how to take the floor (raise hand, chat, reactions) to ensure balanced participation and avoid interruptions.

10

Model empathy, neutrality, and digital respect

Demonstrate patience with language differences, technical issues, and diverse communication styles.

9

LAST REMINDER

LAST REMINDER

Facilitation is ultimately about building trust in the room. Your role is to help participants **listen, reflect, and make decisions together**, all while keeping the group focused on the agreed objectives and guiding everyone toward a clear, shared outcome.

“And remember - enjoy the process! A positive, enthusiastic atmosphere helps participants feel comfortable and engaged. Have fun!”

GOING FURTHER

10

GOING FURTHER

If you want to explore the topic in greater depth, we are happy to share a carefully curated selection of resources. These materials will help you broaden your understanding, deepen your insights, and gain practical ideas that you can apply in your facilitation. Whether you are looking for theoretical background, practical guidance, or examples from other citizen panels, these resources will provide valuable support as you develop your skills.

- [Transforming conflicts involves dismantling oppressive structures, systems, and behaviors](#) (Missions Publiques)
- [Guide to citizens assemblies for citizens assemblies](#) (European Alternatives) ↪ Focus on Chapter 3, Chapter 5, Chapter 8 & Chapter 9
- [Assembling an Assembly Guide](#) (Democracy Next)
- [De Gruyter Handbook of Citizens' Assemblies](#) (Min Reuchamps , Julien Vrydagh and Yanina Welp)
- [Citizens Assemblies: Guide to democracies that work](#) (Marcin Gerwin)
- [Enabling National Initiatives to Take Democracy Beyond Elections](#) (New Democracy) ↪ Focus on Chapter 5
- [How to run a citizens' assembly](#) (Innovation in Democracy)

“

**There's nothing
left to say.**

Now... go for it!
I'm sure you'll be a great facilitator.

Appendix 4. Icebreaking for Intersectionality-Informed Citizens' Assemblies Session

Funded by
the European Union

EU-CIEMBLY Work Package 4 Training Icebreaking for intersectionality-informed Citizens' assemblies

University of Bergamo
19 January 2026

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Why icebreaking activities matters in CAs

Deliberative processes such as CAs require trust building among the citizens, and among citizens and those in charge to conduct and facilitate them (Euroalter, 2024; DemocracyNext, webpage):

"Building trust across the process of an assembly cannot only strengthen participants' sense of political self-efficacy but also empower collective agency and eventually influence the policy impact of the assembly" (Euroalter, 2024)

Crucial to this aim can be creative techniques since the onset of CAs, before the deliberation phase, and in particular **icebreaking activities**.

Such practices can:

- help the participants become comfortable with one another before engaging with substantive issues and become aware of the different intersectional characteristics of the people involved
- reduce self-censorship, particularly among less confident participants
- enhance inclusion, especially for citizens less accustomed to speaking in public settings

Sources:
 DemocracyNext. (2023). Assembling an Assembly: A how-to guide. Retrieved from <https://assemblyguide.demnext.org/>
 Euroalter (2024). GUIDE TO CITIZENS ASSEMBLIES FOR CITIZENS ASSEMBLIES.
<https://euroalter.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Guide-to-citizens-assemblies-for-citizens-assemblies-2.pdf>
 OECD (2020). *Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave*.
<file:///C:/Users/39346/Desktop/UniBG/OECD%20deliberation%20good%20practices.pdf> (p.118)

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Contributing to three core aims...

Break the Ice

Create connection and engagement in a creative, and hopefully funny, way that helps participants feel comfortable with those around them from the very first moments

Explore Positionality

Invite reflection on individual positionality—valuable for personal awareness and group understanding—revealing the diverse backgrounds and intersectional identities present in the room

Understand how Privilege/Power/Disempowerment can affect decision-making/the deliberation phase

Invite to reflect on how power dynamics—that circulate in everyday interactions, institutional settings, and group processes, rather than being held only through formal authority—can impact on the extent to which people interact, and how

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Making ad hoc questions to the participants...

- based on the Wheel of Privilege (or Power Flower), reflecting on their own positionality by physically experiencing how social positions—shaped by intersecting dimensions such as gender, class, race, education, citizenship, ability, etc.—are unevenly distributed in the room
- elaborating on the extent to which certain characteristics can be used as a mean of power and/or they tend to disempower the citizens involved in the CAs
- doing this with specific reference to the object of discussion, i.e., housing

Movement becomes a way to make visible what is often taken for granted or remains implicit.

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Theatre-based icebreaking activity

Movement-based exercise n. 1

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Theatre-based icebreaking activity

Movement-based exercise n. 1

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Theatre-based icebreaking activity

Movement-based exercise n. 1

- An actor/narrator guides the activity by asking a series of questions.
- Participants start on one side of the room, which is divided into two areas by a visible line on the floor.
- In response to each question, participants are invited to cross the line if they recognise themselves in the statement
- Questions are inspired by dimensions of the *Wheel of Privilege* (e.g. age, gender, education, access to services, place of origin) and to studies on power, are tailored to the specific topic of the Assembly (e.g. housing), even if more general questions can be made to make the activity lighter, more engaging and stimulating
- Movement allows participants to visually and physically experience differences and intersections among them, as well as emphasize that certain characteristics can be used as (or give) power to certain individuals but not to others, and/or disempower people. All this without necessarily requiring verbal disclosure.
- However, to stimulate a shared reflection, people can be asked to freely provide explanations, and express their feelings

Icebreaking within the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

Theatre-based icebreaking activity

Movement-based exercise n. 2 (alternative) – adaptable to the online pilot

- It implies the physical mapping of a Wheel of Privilege
- A large printed *Wheel of Privilege* is displayed (for the online version, this could be shared digitally in a online setting).
- Participants place a (physical/virtual) post-it or a small paper marker on the wheel to indicate how they perceive their position in relation to specific dimensions, following the narrator's guidance.
- If they wish, participants can briefly explain their choice (if online, through the chat, the use of online surveys, the use of a diary, the possibility to add notes in an online setting)
- This format is particularly suitable for online Citizen Assemblies, where a shared digital board can be used. When **online**:
 - Shared visual board (e.g., Wheel of Privilege online)
 - Live polls with visual results

For icebreaking purposes...

Micro-pair reflection

Participants briefly turn to the person/s next to them and share a couple of insights and/or feelings that emerged during the exercise.

One word round

Participants who feel comfortable may share one word describing how the activity made them feel (e.g. curious, aware, surprised); others may simply listen or express similar or different feelings.

One-word wall (online-friendly)

Participants write one word or short phrase on a post-it or shared digital board about what they bring into the Assembly and/or about their feelings/perceptions/thoughts/expectations.

General questions to warm up and lighten the situation...

- Who comes from the South/North of the World?
- Who comes from a capital city?
- Who lives near the seaside?
- Who lives in the mountains?
- Who loves reading?
- Who plays a musical instrument?

What questions (valid for both alternatives 1 and 2)

Need to pay attention to...

- Avoid overly intimate or potentially traumatic questions.
- Always make it clear that participants can choose not to move.
- Clarify that adding additional comments, sharing their own emotions, is not mandatory

Example of questions (not dealing with the topic of the CA)

Background/education

Please cross the line if at least one of your parents or caregivers had the opportunity to attend higher education

Background/Wealth

Cross the line if, while growing up, you rarely worried about having enough money to cover basic needs

Example of questions (not dealing with the topic of the CA)

Access, language, perception of legitimacy

Cross the line if the language you feel most comfortable speaking is also the one most commonly used in institutions or public settings.

Cross the line if the way you speak, your accent, or your words have ever made you feel less confident or less legitimate.

Mobility, citizenship, rights

Cross the line if travelling, studying, or working abroad has generally been easy for you from a legal point of view.

Example of questions (not dealing with the topic of the CA)

Power dynamics and deliberation

Power as voice and visibility

Move to the other side if you usually feel comfortable expressing your opinion in group discussions.
 Cross the line if you often hold back, even when you have something important to say.

Decision-making and invisible power

Cross the line if you are often involved in decisions that affect your community or everyday life
 Move to the other side if decisions affecting you are often taken by others
 Cross the line if you have ever thought: 'This is just how things work' and stopped questioning it

Spaces of Power

Cross the line if you are usually invited into spaces where decisions are discussed
 Move to the other side if you have had to create your own spaces to be heard
 Cross the line if you feel able to challenge rules or decisions you disagree with

Example of questions (housing)

Housing security

Please cross the line if you currently feel secure about your housing situation.

Move to the other side if you have experienced uncertainty or instability in your housing in the past.

Cross the line if you have ever felt you had real choice when it came to housing

Example of questions (housing)

Housing and economic resources

Cross the line if your income allows you to choose where to live, rather than just accept what is available.

Move to the other side if housing costs strongly limit your other life choices (work, family, health).

Example of questions (housing)

Origins, language, discrimination

Cross the line if you have never felt disadvantaged in the housing market because of your name, accent, or place of origin.

Move to the other side if you have ever felt treated differently when looking for a home.

Cross the line if your household structure (single, couple, family) usually fits what the housing market expects.

Move to the other side if your family situation /sexuality has made finding suitable housing more difficult.

Example of questions (housing)

Mobility and citizenship

Cross the line if your legal or administrative status has never been an obstacle to renting or owning a home.

Move to the other side if paperwork, permits, or legal conditions have limited your housing options.

Example of questions (housing)

Power dynamics and deliberation

Voice & visibility in housing debates

Move to the other side if you feel your concerns about housing are usually listened to.

Move to the other side if you feel invisible or unheard when it comes to housing issues.

Cross the line if you feel confident engaging with landlords, agencies, or institutions.

Decision-making power

Cross the line if you have real influence over decisions about your housing situation.

Move to the other side if important housing decisions affecting you are mostly taken by others.

Step forward if you have ever accepted housing conditions because you felt you had no alternative.

Spaces of power

Cross the line if you know where and how housing decisions are made in your city.

Step forward if housing policies feel distant or hard to access.

Move to the other side if you feel able to challenge housing rules or decisions you consider unfair.

Breaking the ice while fostering reflexivity

Observational/opinion sharing breaks: *"Take a moment to look around the room..."*

- Where are you standing? Why?
- Who is on the right/left side?
- What do you notice about diversity and similarity in the group?
- If you wish, identify a person near to you (or opposite the line) and take 2 min to share ideas...
- ...

At the end of the game...

- What surprised you in this exercise?
- How might the differences emerged matter when we deliberate together/discuss about housing?
- What voices or experiences should we make sure are not left at the margins in this Assembly?
- To what extent the differences observed characterize also facilitators/etc (in case they take part to the game...)
- Who seems closer to security when it comes to housing? Who to vulnerability?
- What does this tell us about housing as a shared but unequal experience?
- ...

Conclusion

This activity (with its sub-options) should...

- act as an icebreaker while introducing key concepts of intersectionality, privilege, power, disempowerment (one single exercise – time maximisation!)
- help facilitators better understand participants' backgrounds and perspectives, as well as potential biases that may negatively affect the deliberation process and its outputs.
- encourage participants to reflect on how their experiences and positions shape their views, interactions, and contributions within the Assembly.

Questions & answers

Invite questions from the audience.

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Thank you!

Appendix 5. Intersectionality and Facilitation Session

Intersectionality; Positionality & Power

Understanding your role as a facilitator in small groups of diverse citizens across contexts

The Change Agency

We offer training, facilitation and coaching for addressing personal, interpersonal & structural challenges in groups.

Our work **gives you new ways of perceiving old challenges.**

It sparks a transformation and supports you to put your values into practice.

We generate culture change that **enhances collaboration, activates individual expertise and generates more equity.**

Kathryn Mc Cabe/Caitriona Ni Caba

CURRICULUM DESIGN | DELIBERATIVE DEMOCRACY | CAPACITY BUILDING

Social Ecologist and founding Director of The Change Agency, Kathryn brings curiosity, creativity, and integrity to her international work at the intersection of participatory democracy, environmental protection, and social-ecological wellbeing.

She thrives on turning complexity into clarity, designing learning experiences that spark insight, imagination, and action. Kathryn partners with communities, governments, and research institutions to co-create programs and resources that are practical, playful, and transformative.

A skilled facilitator, educator, and change strategist, she navigates cultural and power dynamics with empathy and courage, building connections, fostering collaboration, and nurturing collective action for change and democratic innovation.

Workshop overview

- Begin with an overview of the content and approach already offered.
- Deepen our perspectives of intersectionality.
- Widen our understanding of power.
- Narrow our focus to the interpersonal.

Please type in the chat

What you think or feel about the focus of this project, its potential impacts?

What do you feel about your role? Any specific concerns?

Group discussion on the purpose of including diverse Participants; why is this important?

INTERSECTIONALITY

Intersectionality is a lens through which you can see where power comes and collides, where it locks and intersects. It is the acknowledgement that everyone has their own unique experiences of discrimination and privilege.

– Kimberlé Crenshaw –

@syfraducskorff

Facilitator Positionality Review: Your personal intersecting identity

Choose 6 categories that are most relevant to you.

- See Reflection questions in document
- See Reflexion questions in document

Various aspects inform and shape your identity.

Northcentral University
Diversity Wheel

Our identity may have aspects that are closer or further away from accepted social norms or 'power'.

Note: Adapted from Duckworth (2020) and from Le Dispensaire (n.d.).

Wider systems, (outer ring) that are close to social norms, retain and reinforce power, maintaining what has 'value'.

Oppressive Systems impact us all (differently)
and at all scales

Causes and impact of racial marginalisation, at each scale

Spectrum of impact of oppressive systems; lower 3 areas

Patterns of Covert Oppression

- Belief in one right way
- Either/or thinking
- Denial of privilege 'Right to comfort'
- Power Hoarding
- Perfectionism
- Sense of Urgency
- Micro-aggressions
- Toxic positivity (good vibes only)
- Tone policing
- Interrupting
- Minimising
- Micromanagement
- Defensiveness/fragility (centreing self)
- Resistant to open disagreements
- Intellectualising
- Fixing/savior mentality
- Macro-aggression (centering white values and culture)
- Progress = bigger better more
- Bootstrap/trickle down theory
- Quantity over quality
- Individualism
- Meritocracy (best person for the job)
- Focus on outputs/measurements and data
- Incentives and punishments
- Paternalism

Diversity without Inclusion

Adapted from "The Chronicle of the Problem Woman of Color in a Non-Profit" by the Sabatosa Progressive Alliance for Nonviolence

None of our actions are neutral, but we can learn to see I biases, and the structures that uphold them.

We can learn to step DOWN the staircase of oppression; sharing power, acting in allyship in situations of discrimination or exclusion, understanding how our values, and beliefs have been shaped by experience.

How can we approach our roles?

We use the term **‘mutual interest’** to help us move from the idea of helping others, or just thinking about what is good for us, to understanding that our own liberation as white people, our own humanity, is inextricably linked to racial justice.

Mutual interest means we cannot overcome the challenges we face unless we work for racial justice. It means our own freedom is bound up in the freedom of people of color.

[Showing Up for Racial Justice \(SURJ\)](#)

What is Inclusion?

Table 1. Elements of inclusion

Fairness and respect	Value and belonging	Confidence and inspiration
Foundational element that is underpinned by ideas about equality of treatment and opportunities	Individuals feeling that their uniqueness is known and appreciated, while also feeling a sense of social connectedness and group membership	Creating the conditions for high team performance through individuals having the confidence to speak up and the motivation to do their best work

<https://www.aldenhabacon.com>

Learning to work 'safely', inclusively across diversity in not complicated, its complex

Reflection and reflexion on our identities, the impact of wider systems and how we engage interpersonally requires **unlearning** as well as learning.

@HOLISTICALLYGRACE

FIXED - COMFORT	GROWTH - COURAGE
"I DON'T KNOW WHERE TO START OR WHAT TO SAY"	"FIRST I WILL LISTEN/READ/WATCH. I WILL SPEAK AGAINST INJUSTICE"
"I DON'T WANT TO GET IT WRONG OR GET CALLED OUT"	"I WILL MAKE MISTAKES, NO DOUBT ABOUT IT. I WILL BE GRATEFUL FOR THE LESSON"
"IT WON'T MAKE A DIFFERENCE WHAT I DO, NOTHING IS GOING TO CHANGE"	"THINGS HAPPEN WHEN I TAKE RISKS AND BECOME PART OF SOMETHING BIGGER"
"I DON'T GET INVOLVED IN POLITICS. I DON'T HAVE TIME"	"THIS IS A HUMAN RIGHTS ISSUE. THIS MATTERS, I WILL"

"One of the fastest ways to learn interdependence is to **shift how we show up in relationship**. Primarily, we get more honest... Radical Honesty... ask the questions you really want answered, speak your truth and let the relationship build inside all that reality" Adrienne Maree Brown

Intersectional Facilitators are people who

- care,
- educate themselves; **understand their context** of power and oppression,
- know their privilege, and **use it well**,
- **curate a space** for those typically marginalised to **take up more space**,
- follow the leadership of marginalised communities,
- are **active** bystanders,
- act in situations of **discomfort**,
- speak in situations of tension; that name the moment, accepts it and **enquires with curiosity** about it,
- **step in, name the system**, rather than focusing only on the personal,
- accept feedback, seek **feedback**,
- use their own privilege to create change.

Approaches to foster as facilitators

Strengthen perspective of **mutual interest**

Value others perspectives, views and experiences as **equally valid**

Apply ethics; nuanced, curious, firm when necessary

Develop comfort with tension and uncertainty

Accept we are imperfect, practice being open to making **mistakes** and hearing feedback

Manage response to own 'triggers'

Relational; Values **process** and not just outcome

Seeks connection, builds relationships and fosters **conditions for consent**

WHY WE DON'T TONE POLICE

- "I agree, but the way your message was delivered was..." or "Instead of attacking, why don't we educate..." or "Seems like you're really upset, let's all remain civil..." are examples of tone policing.
- Tone policing is a way to silence the oppressed. It derails from the message.
- The oppressor does not get to define how the oppressed advocates for themselves.
- Tone policing is an act of avoidance, gaslighting, and control.
- If your allyhood is contingent on "niceness," then it is a false allyhood.

@ALEXJENNY_

HOW TO RECEIVE FEEDBACK

- Do not react defensively.
- Do not make this about you.
- Do not center your emotional process.
- Suspend judgement.
- Listen to understand.
- Summarize and reflect what you heard.
Check for shared understanding.
- Ask clarifying questions.
- Ask for feedback from others.
- Share your appreciation for receiving

BUILDING TOLERANCE FOR FEEDBACK

- Ask for feedback, often. Practice.
- Notice how you instinctually react to feedback (defensiveness, body tension, impulse to protect your character, white guilt and tears, etc.) and identify how you would like to react instead.
- Sit with the discomfort of being called out.
- Build tolerance for holding space for the rage, grief, anger, and distrust of BIPOC.

Some wider ideas for action

Prioritise safer spaces

- Communication and conflict skills training and *practice*
- Power-sharing decision making
- Collaboration across typically separate areas
- Single identity spaces with purpose and interdependencies built in
- Sharing our identities and intersections as a tool for harm reduction
- Sniff out the covert cultural norms; learn, feedback, apologies, do better
- Seek feedback, welcome it
- Co-design accountability measures

Reparations:

- Frontline staff offered free weekly therapy
- Single identity spaces
- Avenues for addressing issues without risking harm
- Individualised contracts

Power sharing:

- Transparent salary and payments
- Transparent roles and hours
- Clear pathways of decision making
- Demonstrated accountability
- Review and amend harms

Longer term:

- Distributed decision making eg sociocracY
- Training for all staff on equity perspectives
- Phase out board members with limited lived experience of inequity.
- Review and publicly discuss the legacy or context of the work. Be specific.
- Take accountability measures

Summary

People who have experienced marginalisation can be liberated through an understanding of the systems that have oppressed and excluded them.

People with areas of privilege can learn to use their positionality to enable more equitable access to power.

Commonalities can be found more easily with a shared understanding of oppressive systems and how, together, we can alter how power functions across various scales (personal, interpersonal and structural).